

Solvent Extraction of Ruthenium(III) from Chloride Solution with Cinnamoylhydroxamic Acid in Isobutyl Alcohol

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THE present paper describes the extraction of ruthenium from aqueous chloride solutions into isobutyl alcohol in the form of its complex with cinnamoylhydroxamic acid (CHA). The extraction photometric procedure is also adopted to evaluate certain extraction parameters.

Experimental

The reagent cinnamoylhydroxamic acid (CHA) was prepared by the literature procedure¹. The reagent was recrystallised and its purity was confirmed by checking its melting point, and by C, H, N analyses. A stock solution of ruthenium(III) was prepared by dissolving ruthenium chloride (1.0 g; 99.9%, Arora Mathey) in 0.1M HCl (100 ml). Buffer solutions of different pH were prepared by mixing 1.0 N acetic acid and 1.0 N NaOH in appropriate volumes².

pH measurements were done with a Systronics 335 digital pH-meter. A Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer was used for the measurement of absorbances.

Procedure: Distribution equilibria at different pH were studied by shaking the aqueous solution (10 ml; $9.74 \times 10^{-5} M$) of ruthenium(III) chloride buffered with acetate solutions and 0.05 M solution of CHA in isobutyl alcohol (10 ml). Two phases were separated after the attainment of the equilibrium. The organic extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and its absorbance was measured at 340 nm against reagent blank. The equilibrium pH of the aqueous phases were measured for each of the solutions. The organic extract gave maximum absorbance at pH 5.9, so the other studies were done at this pH.

In order to study the effect of reagent concentration, the following procedure was adopted. Each 10 ml of aqueous phase buffered at pH 5.9 containing the same amount ($9.74 \times 10^{-5} M$) of Ru^{III} was shaken with isobutyl alcoholic solution (10 ml) of CHA of varying concentrations. After equilibration, the organic phases were separated, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbances were measured as stated before.

The effect of chloride ion concentrations was studied over the range 0.005–1.0 M by adding NaCl at a fixed pH 5.9 and fixed reagent concentration 0.01 M. Mole-ratio method was used to determine the metal-ligand ratio and the stability constant of the extractable complex.

Results and Discussion

The experimental data indicate that the ruthenium extraction with CHA is not dependent on chloride ion concentration. The metal:ligand ratio was found to be 1:3 by Job's method as well as by mole-ratio method. This suggested the extraction to occur according to equilibria,

The log *D* vs log [HL]_o plot gave a straight line of slope equal to 2.87, when *D* (distribution ratio for the metal) = [ML_{n(o)}]/[Mⁿ⁺], [HL]_o is the reagent concentration in organic phase, and *K*_{ex} the extraction constant. This value of nearly 3 further confirmed the metal:ligand ratio of 1:3 and also indicated the extracted complex to be a electro-neutral RuL₃ species. The average value of log *K*_{ex} was found to be -10.11 ± 0.09 .

The stepwise formation constants were evaluated by Leden's method as modified by Bag and coworkers³ and were found to be log *K*₁ = 2.20, log *K*₂ = 2.73 and log *K*₃ = 3.60. The increasing trend of the values of *K*₁, *K*₂ and *K*₃ is, however, against the general statistical order. Determination of the factor(s) responsible for such findings requires an extensive QSAR (quantitative structure activity relationship) study, which is presently in progress.

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Bis-4-phthalanilic Acid Sulphone : A New Specific Gravimetric Reagent for Copper(II)

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IN this communication, synthesis of new chelating agent, viz. bis-4-phthalanilic acid sulphone is reported and its potential for microdetection as well as gravimetric estimation of copper in presence

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of large number of metal ions without using masking agents have been presented.

Experimental

Stock solution of copper(II) chloride (AnalaR) was prepared in double-distilled water using least quantity of acetic acid. The copper contents of the solution was determined gravimetrically using benzoic acid and NH_4SCN reagents¹ separately.

Synthesis of reagents : Bis-4-phthalianilic acid sulphone was prepared by the condensation of bis-4-aminophenyl sulphone (I.P., a well known antileprocy drug; 1 mol) with phthalic anhydride (2 mol) in absolute alcohol.

Bis-4-phthalianilic acid sulphone separated on cooling was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol as white crystals and its purity was checked by sulphur estimation as BaSO_4 (92%), m.p. 157° (Found: S, 5.87. Calcd. S, 5.89%). A 0.2 M ethanolic solution of the reagent was used for qualitative and quantitative estimation of copper.

Determination of copper : An aqueous solution of cupric chloride (containing about 2–254 mg Cu) was diluted to 50 ml. pH of the solution was adjusted ~ 6.5 using dilute KOH. The solution was warmed to $60-70^\circ$ and a 0.2% ethanolic solution of the reagent (25 ml per 330 mg of Cu) was added with constant stirring until complete precipitation occurred. It was digested the resulting green shining over a water-bath for 0.5 h or preferably keeping overnight, and the resulting green shining crystals of the copper complex filtered cold through a sintered glass crucible (G-4), washed with water and dried at $120-30^\circ$ (Found: N, 4.60; S, 5.31; Cu, 10.46. $\text{C}_{58}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2\text{Cu}_2$ calcd.: N, 4.62; S, 5.29; Cu, 10.49%). Tables 1 and 2 illustrate the results.

Effect of foreign ion : The effect of foreign ions was studied by adding different amounts of foreign ions to 25.41 mg of Cu^{II} and estimating the copper contents by stated procedure. It was found that Al^{III} , Tl^{IV} , V^{V} , Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Ag^{I} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} , Pb^{II} , Sn^{II} , Sn^{IV} , As^{III} , W^{VI} , Bi^{III} , Sb^{V} , Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} , Ba^{II} , Ce^{IV} , UO_2^{II} , Na , $\text{CrO}_4^{\text{2-}}$, ClO_4^- , NO_3^- , Cl^- , CH_3COO^- , $\text{BO}_3^{\text{3-}}$, $\text{PO}_4^{\text{3-}}$, Br^- , F^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{\text{2-}}$, chromate, chlorate, nitrate, fluoride, chloride, bromide, borate, phosphate, thiosulphate and

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF COPPER AS BIS-4-PHTHALIANILIC ACID SULPHONE COMPLEX

Cu taken mg	Cu found mg	% Error
2.541	2.537	-0.16
5.082	5.075	-0.14
12.705	12.739	+0.27
25.410	25.385	-0.10
38.115	38.019	-0.25
50.820	50.685	-0.27
63.525	63.737	+0.33
127.050	126.698	-0.28
190.575	190.127	-0.24
254.100	253.405	-0.27

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN B. C. S. STANDARD* SAMPLES

Sample	Cu found mg	Certified value mg	Standard deviation
8C White metal	4.12, 4.08, 4.11, 4.09	4.10	0.02
5F Brass	70.74, 70.74, 70.72, 70.75	70.80	0.08
6F gun metal	87.86, 87.84, 87.94, 87.92	87.90	0.05

*British Chemical Standard.

acetate did not interfere even present in considerable amounts. However thiocyanide, iodide and nitrate interfered even if present in traces.

Determination of copper in alloys : A sample of the alloy was dissolved in concentrated nitric acid and evaporated to dryness. The procedure was repeated thrice and finally the residue was dissolved in minimum quantity of hydrochloric acid. The solution was made up to 100 ml with distilled water. An aliquot (25 ml) of the solution was taken, diluted to 50 ml and the copper was precipitated with the reagent by the stated procedure (Table 2).

Results and Discussion

The reagent solution reacts with cupric ions even in low concentration (7×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3}) yielding heavy shining green crystals at pH ~ 6.5 . However, dissociation of the complex started on increasing or decreasing the pH of the solution. Diverse ions as stated above showed no reaction with the reagent at any concentration under the conditions of the experiment. The copper chelate did not melt up to 250° but darkened above this temperature.

Ten determinations, employing 25.41 mg of Cu^{II} each were carried out. The standard deviation and coefficient of variance were found to be ± 0.018 and 0.072 respectively. Determination of copper in alloys (Table 2) were also found accurate with minimum value of standard deviation. Analytical data correspond to the regression equation $Y = 0.00145 + 0.1091X$, where X and Y are respectively the weights of isolated complex and copper found in it.

Reference

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